

Scenario overview from the BIRD project (Bildungsraum Digital)

category	Name	DOI	Components	Tools & Services	Persona	DOI Persona
Generally	SZ-A-01: Registration at BIRD via BUND-ID	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10090359	DATA WALLET	BUND.ID	P: Alvin - Parent	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091406
I. Inform	SZ-SB-I-04: School transfer to a different state	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10090761	LEARNINGPATHFINDER CHAT DATA WALLET	BIRD CALENDAR	P: Alvin - Parent	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091406
	SZ-HB-I-03: Search for a second degree studies	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10090660	DATA WALLET LEARNINGPATHFINDER WORKSPACE	ONLINE SELF ASSESSMENT HOCHSCHULSTART	P: Carlotta - Adult education	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14615153
	SZ-SB-I-07: Search for an apprenticeship	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10090699	DATA WALLET LEARNINGPATHFINDER CHATBOT		P: Kim - Pupil	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091312
	SZ-SB-I-09: Searching for information about a teacher studies course in music	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10090736	DATA WALLET LEARNINGPATHFINDER WORKSPACE	VIDEO CONFERENCE TEXT EDITOR	P: Greta - Pupil	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091323
	SZ-HB-I-01: Research the language requirements for an exchange semester	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14930909	DATA WALLET LEARNINGPATHFINDER WORKSPACE		P: Kaja - Student	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091286
	SZ-HB-I-02: Search for a master's program	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10090628	PROFILE WORKSPACE CHAT LEARNINGPATHFINDER		P: Nadine - Student	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091292
	SZ-EB-I-01: Connecting a state-owned Moodle platform	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15437092	LEARNINGPATHFINDER	MOODLE	P: Simon - Adult education	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15261088
II. Collect and elaborate	SZ-HB-II-01-02: Planing an exchange Semester	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091353	LEARNINGPATHFINDER WORKSPACE CHAT	VIDEO CONFERENCE	P: Kaja - Student	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091286

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	SZ-BB-II-01-01: Keeping a training record	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14851112	CHAT WORKSPACE	IHK REPORT BOOKLET	P: Claudia - Trainer P: Jasper - Trainee	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13644649 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091281
	SZ-HB-II-02-02: Continuing to use a course from another LMS	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15259918	WORKSPACE	STUD.IP MOODLE	P: Emil - Professor	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13684426
	SZ-HB-II-02-04: Completing and sharing a course with other teachers	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15261192	WORKSPACE	MOODLE	P: Emil - Professor	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13684426
	SZ-HB-II-02-07: Connecting to cloud storage and collaborative work	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14851197	CHAT WORKSPACE	TEXT EDITOR ANNOTATION TASK LIST OPEN OLAF	P: Vladimir - Student P: Kaja - Student	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13359054 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091286
	SZ-HB-02-08: Search for a course at another university	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15261291	LEARNINGPATHFINDER PROFILE CONTACTS	STUD.IP	P: Nadine - Student	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091292
	SZ-HB-02-09: Taking a course at another university	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15261343	LEARNINGPATHFINDER WORKSPACE	STUD.IP	P: Nadine - Student	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091292
	SZ-BB-II-02-02: Creating a presentation together	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14851216	WORKSPACE CHAT CONTACTS	HAIKU CHECK TEXT EDITOR	P: Jasper - Trainee	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091281
III. detect and connect	SZ-SB-III-01-01: Self-Assessment-Test and search for a tutor	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091416	DATA WALLET LEARNINGPATHFINDER CHAT BUDDYFINDER		P: Mark - Pupil	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13643228
	SZ-SB-III-01-02: Networking among teachers	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10090506	LEARNINGPATHFINDER CHAT	VIDEO CONFERENCE	P: Selin - Teacher	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091270

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	from different schools		BUDDYFINDER WORKSPACE			
	SZ-SB-III-01-03: Networking between parents from different schools	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14851233	BUDDYFINDER CHAT LEARNINGPATHFINDER		P: Alvin - Parent	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091406
	SZ-HB-III-01-01: Search for other prospective Students	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091489	DATA WALLET BUDDYFINDER CHAT	VIDEO CONFERENCE CALENDAR	P: Carlotta - Adult education	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14615153
	SZ-HB-III-01-02: A (university) applicant looking for students	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091551	BUDDYFINDER CHAT CONTACTS	VIDEO CONFERENCE	P: Greta - Pupil	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091323
	SZ-HB-III-01-06: Search for inclusion specialist for professional exchange	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091497	CHAT BUDDYFINDER WORKSPACE		P: Nadine - Student	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091292
	SZ-BB-III-01-01: Networking of vocational school pupil from different vocational schools	https://zenodo.org/records/10091462	LEARNINGPATHFINDER CHAT BUDDYFINDER WORKSPACE	VIDEO CONFERENCE	P: Jasper - Trainee	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091281
	SZ-SB-III-02-01: Search for other pupil	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091507	DATA WALLET BUDDYFINDER CHAT WORKSPACE		P: Lisa - Pupil	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13682752
	SZ-SB-III-02-02: Search for other Teachers	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091531	BUDDYFINDER WORKSPACE CHAT		P: Selin - Teacher	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091270
	SZ-HB-III-02-01: Search for other students to prepare for exams	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091519	BUDDYFINDER CHAT	STUDOCO	P: Nadine - Student	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091292
	SZ-SB-III-03-01: Contacting	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14851258	BUDDYFINDER CHAT		P: Alvin - Parent	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091406

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	teachers via BIRD		CONTACTS PROFILE			